
TRANSIENT STABILITY ASSESSMENT OF MULTI-MACHINE POWER SYSTEMS USING SWING CURVE AND STATCOM INTEGRATION

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>Voltage stability is increasingly important in modern power systems due to rising network complexity, higher power demands, widespread integration of large generation units and longdistance transmission lines. The bus voltage magnitude tends to decrease continuously due to disturbances and can cause voltage collapse if the network topology and reactive power support are insufficient. This article examines voltage stability on the IEEE 30-bus test system under transient fault conditions. It assesses the role of a Static Synchronous Compensator (STATCOM) in enhancing voltage stability during a three-phase fault. A load-flow analysis was carried out using the Newton-Raphson method. Buses 14 and 24 are identified as weak buses, with highly connected transmission lines and located far from the generator bus. These buses are candidates for the system voltage stability study because they have insufficient reactive power and are likely to collapse under fault conditions. The network was modified by installing STATCOMs on Buses 14 and 24 to improve their reactive power support. The reactive power compensation applied by the STATCOM is done by the injection of reactive power of 0.4760 p.u and 0.5628 p.u at buses 14 and 24 respectively. The behaviour of the system during faults at buses 14 and 24, respectively, was investigated under the same clearing time of 0.1sec and simulation time of 2.0 secs by removing lines 14-15 and 23-24, respectively. The study demonstrates that STATCOM improves the system voltage stability margin in a faulty power system.</p>	<p>Hunting, Droop settings, Swing curve, STATCOM, Voltage stability, Critical clearing time.</p>

Introduction

It is necessary to provide a reliable, continuous electric power supply under various loading conditions. In power system operation, loads are dynamic and time-dependent (Jokojeje et al., 2018). Variation in loads is regarded as a disturbance. The system responds by absorbing the shock and assumes another operating point to maintain power system stability. When the system is operating at a small load, steady-state stability is maintained. This

means that the reactive power is sufficient, thereby keeping the voltage magnitudes of various buses within an acceptable limit of $\pm 5\%$, and no transmission lines or cables are overloaded (Moses and Oludolapo, 2023). But at large loads, reactive power may become insufficient, and the voltage magnitude may no longer be within acceptable limits (Ogundare and Alayande, 2009). Consequently, this causes overload on some transmission lines and large voltage drops on others. Before conducting the fault study, all bus voltages must be within acceptable limits, and all transmission lines must be operating within their rated values (Oputa and Madueme, 2019). Since the network should be in a steady state before a fault is applied, STATCOM is used to inject reactive power into buses that fall out of the statutory voltage limit. If a fault is suddenly applied to a bus in a network operating at steady state, the generators' rotors will experience oscillation about another operating point (Fetissi, Laabed, 2015). It will take the generator a finite amount of time to settle at another point of operation depending on the level of fault and the network topology. Otherwise, the rotor continues to oscillate. Transient stability is determined from the nature of the swing curve. If the curve returns to the pre-fault level or a new level after some time, the system is stable. However, if the rotor angle continues to increase indefinitely with the first oscillation exceeding the critical angle and continues to increase, the system is unstable. The system is said to have transient stability if the oscillation dies out within a few cycles of the operating frequency. The maximum duration for which the fault must be cleared to maintain stability is called the critical clearing time (CCT) (Wang, Tang and Xu, 2015). It is the time between the initiation of the fault and its clearance. However, if the fault-clearing time exceeds the CCT, rotor oscillation continues indefinitely, leading to cascading faults and ultimately voltage collapse. Timely fault clearing increases the reliability of the electric power supply. Therefore, Knowledge of CCT is essential for monitoring the power system transient stability, protection scheme and response under various operating conditions.

Power system stability in a multi-machine system concerns the synchronisation of generators operating at a constant frequency and voltage, given that the phase sequence of each machine is the same (Ogundare *et al.*, 2022). A generator operating at no load will operate at its rated speed (and therefore its frequency) and voltage. When the load is applied, the speed drops. The governor controls the speed of a generator. Thus, a generator has a droop characteristic. Droop is a graph of speed versus load, also called a droop curve. Droop creates elasticity in the response of the governor thereby enabling load sharing among the generators (Wang, Tang and Xu, 2015). If a generator does not have droop, it will attempt to correct the speed rigidly and instantly. This type of response would cause hunting, oscillation and eventual loss of synchronism. The droop characteristics of a generator enable it to carry the load gradually and smoothly. The grid frequency is determined by all generators connected synchronously. Since all generators connected in parallel have similar droop settings, they automatically share the load and remain stable when the total load is less than the sum of the generators' rated values. The generators shared the load according to their sizes and droop settings. If the system is operating within the CCT, the generators run synchronously; however, the voltage magnitude is controlled in this article using STATCOM to prevent voltage collapse. STATCOM is incorporated into the weak buses to support reactive power.

This paper is structured into four sections: Section 1 provides a detailed introduction to the article; Section 2 presents the materials and methods, including power-flow equations, FACTS device modelling, and data for the sample network. Section three presents the results and discussion, while section four provides the conclusion.

Several publications on power system stability have appeared in the literature. The authors' presentation in (Ogundare *et al.*, 2024) explains the use of the synchronous power coefficient (SPC) to determine the system's steady-state stability in a multi-machine power system. The article investigated generator synchronisation without considering voltage stability. It was found that the system is stable when the

change in active power with respect to rotor angle is positive, and unstable otherwise. The study presented in (Ogundare *et al.*, 2025) considered the use of SPC, the incorporation of SVC on weak buses, and the addition of parallel transmission lines to topologically weak transmission lines. The authors did not consider introducing faults into the system. In the work presented by the authors in (Ogundare *et al.*, 2024), voltage stability improvement was achieved using an SVC, with faults introduced to the power system to determine the bus-breaking capacity. A shortcoming of this work is the lack of investigation into synchronisation. Optimal SVC placement was performed in the study by the authors (Adebisi *et al.*, 2024) to assess improvements in voltage stability. The study did not address power system synchronisation. In recent years, Flexible Ac Transmission Systems (FACTS) have received more comprehensive attention, most especially in power system stability assessment. In prior research works, many authors have used different types of FACTS (SVC, TCSC, SSCC *etc*) for different applications in power systems. In this work, STATCOM is used to enhance power system stability using the Newton-Raphson iterative model.

Load-Flow Modelling Using the Newton-Raphson Method

The Newton-Raphson iterative method is commonly used to solve systems of simultaneous nonlinear algebraic equations. The static power flow equations are given by (1) and (2) (Ogundar *et al.*, 202022)

$$P_i = \sum_{k=1}^N |V_i| |V_k| [G_{ik} \sin(\delta_i - \delta_k) - B_{ik} \cos(\delta_i - \delta_k)] \tag{1}$$

$$Q_i = \sum_{k=1}^N |V_i| |V_k| [G_{ik} \cos(\delta_i - \delta_k) + B_{ik} \sin(\delta_i - \delta_k)] \tag{2}$$

The known and unknown vectors at the various buses in the power systems can be written as (3) [10]

$$\begin{bmatrix} P \\ Q \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} J_1 & J_2 \\ J_3 & J_4 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \delta \\ V \end{bmatrix} \tag{3}$$

Where the Jacobian matrix of the network is

$$J = \begin{bmatrix} J_1 & J_2 \\ J_3 & J_4 \end{bmatrix} \tag{4}$$

$$P = P_{sch} - P_{cal} \text{ for both PV and PQ buses} \tag{5}$$

$$Q = Q_{sch} - Q_{cal} \text{ for PQ buses only} \tag{6}$$

The Jacobian matrix J can further be split into off-diagonal elements:

$$J_{1,ik} = \frac{\partial P_i}{\partial \delta_k}, J_{2,ik} = \frac{\partial Q_i}{\partial \delta_k}, J_{3,ik} = \frac{\partial P_i}{\partial V_k} \text{ and } J_{4,ik} = \frac{\partial Q_i}{\partial V_k} \tag{7}$$

$$J_{1,ii} = \frac{\partial P_i}{\partial \delta_i}, J_{2,ii} = \frac{\partial Q_i}{\partial \delta_i}, J_{3,ii} = \frac{\partial P_i}{\partial V_i} \text{ and } J_{4,ii} = \frac{\partial Q_i}{\partial V_i} \tag{8}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} P \\ Q \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} J_1 & J_2 \\ J_3 & J_4 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \delta \\ V \end{bmatrix}$$

Once the unknown vectors $\Delta \delta$ and ΔV are calculated from equation (3) using Gaussian elimination technique, the updated values of the voltage magnitude and voltage angle at the buses can then be found as

$$V_{new} = V_{old} + \Delta V \tag{9}$$

$$V_{new} = V_{old} + \Delta V \tag{10}$$

STATCOM Modelling for Voltage Stability Analysis

The voltage stability can be improved by integrating the three-phase STATCOM model into the three-phase power-flow formulation. In this simulation, the STATCOM’s buses where it is connected are represented as PV or generator buses. These buses can change to PQ buses when, during the process, one of the limits (reactive power) in the device’s voltage magnitudes is violated. The main purpose is to compensate for the reactive power in the power systems and thereby enhance voltage support (Kundur, 2004).

STATCOM is modeled in this work as a voltage source comprising a coupling transformer, a converter, and a DC capacitor, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: STATCOM simple model

Thevenin equivalent circuit of the modelled STATCOM is shown in Figure 2 below

Figure 2: Thevenin equivalent circuit

By considering the equivalent circuit shown in Figure 2 above, the real and reactive power flow constraints of the model are given by:

$$P_{st} = V_p^2 G_{st} - V_p V_{st} (G_{st} \cos(\delta_p - \delta_{st}) + B_{st} \sin(\delta_p - \delta_{st})) \tag{11}$$

$$Q_{st} = -V_p^2 B_{st} - V_p V_{st} (G_{st} \sin(\delta_p - \delta_{st}) - B_{st} \cos(\delta_p - \delta_{st})) \tag{12}$$

where V_{st} is the STATCOM voltage,

V_p is the bus p voltage and the line admittance due to STATCOM is

1

$$Y_{st} = \frac{1}{Z_{st}} = G_{st} + jB_{st} \quad (13)$$

The main constraint of STATCOM operation is that the active power exchange via the DC link must be zero. i.e.

$$e(V_{st} I_{st}^*) = V^2 p_{Gst} - V_p V_{st} (G_{st} \cos(\theta_p - \theta_{st}) + B_{st} \sin(\theta_p - \theta_{st})) = 0 \quad (14)$$

The bus control restraint F is given by

$$F = V_p - V_{sp} = 0 \quad (15)$$

where V_{sp} is the specified voltage at the bus.

By substituting equations (12)-(15) into equation (3), we have equation (16)

$$\begin{bmatrix}
 P_1 \\
 P_2 \\
 \vdots \\
 P_n \\
 e_1 \\
 e_2 \\
 \vdots \\
 e_n \\
 f_1 \\
 f_2 \\
 \vdots \\
 f_n \\
 Q_1 \\
 Q_2 \\
 \vdots \\
 Q_n
 \end{bmatrix}
 =
 \begin{bmatrix}
 P_{11} & P_{12} & \dots & P_{1n} & P_{1e_1} & P_{1e_2} & \dots & P_{1e_n} & P_{1f_1} & P_{1f_2} & \dots & P_{1f_n} & P_{1Q_1} & P_{1Q_2} & \dots & P_{1Q_n} \\
 P_{21} & P_{22} & \dots & P_{2n} & P_{2e_1} & P_{2e_2} & \dots & P_{2e_n} & P_{2f_1} & P_{2f_2} & \dots & P_{2f_n} & P_{2Q_1} & P_{2Q_2} & \dots & P_{2Q_n} \\
 \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\
 P_{n1} & P_{n2} & \dots & P_{nn} & P_{ne_1} & P_{ne_2} & \dots & P_{ne_n} & P_{nf_1} & P_{nf_2} & \dots & P_{nf_n} & P_{nQ_1} & P_{nQ_2} & \dots & P_{nQ_n} \\
 P_{e_11} & P_{e_12} & \dots & P_{e_1n} & P_{e_1e_1} & P_{e_1e_2} & \dots & P_{e_1e_n} & P_{e_1f_1} & P_{e_1f_2} & \dots & P_{e_1f_n} & P_{e_1Q_1} & P_{e_1Q_2} & \dots & P_{e_1Q_n} \\
 P_{e_21} & P_{e_22} & \dots & P_{e_2n} & P_{e_2e_1} & P_{e_2e_2} & \dots & P_{e_2e_n} & P_{e_2f_1} & P_{e_2f_2} & \dots & P_{e_2f_n} & P_{e_2Q_1} & P_{e_2Q_2} & \dots & P_{e_2Q_n} \\
 \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\
 P_{e_n1} & P_{e_n2} & \dots & P_{e_nn} & P_{e_ne_1} & P_{e_ne_2} & \dots & P_{e_ne_n} & P_{e_nf_1} & P_{e_nf_2} & \dots & P_{e_nf_n} & P_{e_nQ_1} & P_{e_nQ_2} & \dots & P_{e_nQ_n} \\
 P_{f_11} & P_{f_12} & \dots & P_{f_1n} & P_{f_1e_1} & P_{f_1e_2} & \dots & P_{f_1e_n} & P_{f_1f_1} & P_{f_1f_2} & \dots & P_{f_1f_n} & P_{f_1Q_1} & P_{f_1Q_2} & \dots & P_{f_1Q_n} \\
 P_{f_21} & P_{f_22} & \dots & P_{f_2n} & P_{f_2e_1} & P_{f_2e_2} & \dots & P_{f_2e_n} & P_{f_2f_1} & P_{f_2f_2} & \dots & P_{f_2f_n} & P_{f_2Q_1} & P_{f_2Q_2} & \dots & P_{f_2Q_n} \\
 \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\
 P_{f_n1} & P_{f_n2} & \dots & P_{f_nn} & P_{f_ne_1} & P_{f_ne_2} & \dots & P_{f_ne_n} & P_{f_nf_1} & P_{f_nf_2} & \dots & P_{f_nf_n} & P_{f_nQ_1} & P_{f_nQ_2} & \dots & P_{f_nQ_n} \\
 P_{Q_11} & P_{Q_12} & \dots & P_{Q_1n} & P_{Q_1e_1} & P_{Q_1e_2} & \dots & P_{Q_1e_n} & P_{Q_1f_1} & P_{Q_1f_2} & \dots & P_{Q_1f_n} & P_{Q_1Q_1} & P_{Q_1Q_2} & \dots & P_{Q_1Q_n} \\
 P_{Q_21} & P_{Q_22} & \dots & P_{Q_2n} & P_{Q_2e_1} & P_{Q_2e_2} & \dots & P_{Q_2e_n} & P_{Q_2f_1} & P_{Q_2f_2} & \dots & P_{Q_2f_n} & P_{Q_2Q_1} & P_{Q_2Q_2} & \dots & P_{Q_2Q_n} \\
 \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\
 P_{Q_n1} & P_{Q_n2} & \dots & P_{Q_nn} & P_{Q_ne_1} & P_{Q_ne_2} & \dots & P_{Q_ne_n} & P_{Q_nf_1} & P_{Q_nf_2} & \dots & P_{Q_nf_n} & P_{Q_nQ_1} & P_{Q_nQ_2} & \dots & P_{Q_nQ_n}
 \end{bmatrix}
 \begin{bmatrix}
 V_1 \\
 V_2 \\
 \vdots \\
 V_n \\
 e_1 \\
 e_2 \\
 \vdots \\
 e_n \\
 f_1 \\
 f_2 \\
 \vdots \\
 f_n \\
 Q_1 \\
 Q_2 \\
 \vdots \\
 Q_n
 \end{bmatrix}
 =
 \begin{bmatrix}
 P_{11} \\
 P_{12} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{1n} \\
 P_{1e_1} \\
 P_{1e_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{1e_n} \\
 P_{1f_1} \\
 P_{1f_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{1f_n} \\
 P_{1Q_1} \\
 P_{1Q_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{1Q_n} \\
 P_{21} \\
 P_{22} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{2n} \\
 P_{2e_1} \\
 P_{2e_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{2e_n} \\
 P_{2f_1} \\
 P_{2f_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{2f_n} \\
 P_{2Q_1} \\
 P_{2Q_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{2Q_n} \\
 \vdots \\
 \vdots \\
 \ddots \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{ne_1} \\
 P_{ne_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{ne_n} \\
 P_{nf_1} \\
 P_{nf_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{nf_n} \\
 P_{nQ_1} \\
 P_{nQ_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{nQ_n} \\
 P_{e_11} \\
 P_{e_12} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{e_1n} \\
 P_{e_1e_1} \\
 P_{e_1e_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{e_1e_n} \\
 P_{e_1f_1} \\
 P_{e_1f_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{e_1f_n} \\
 P_{e_1Q_1} \\
 P_{e_1Q_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{e_1Q_n} \\
 P_{e_21} \\
 P_{e_22} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{e_2n} \\
 P_{e_2e_1} \\
 P_{e_2e_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{e_2e_n} \\
 P_{e_2f_1} \\
 P_{e_2f_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{e_2f_n} \\
 P_{e_2Q_1} \\
 P_{e_2Q_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{e_2Q_n} \\
 \vdots \\
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 \ddots \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{e_ne_1} \\
 P_{e_ne_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{e_ne_n} \\
 P_{e_nf_1} \\
 P_{e_nf_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{e_nf_n} \\
 P_{e_nQ_1} \\
 P_{e_nQ_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{e_nQ_n} \\
 P_{f_11} \\
 P_{f_12} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{f_1n} \\
 P_{f_1e_1} \\
 P_{f_1e_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{f_1e_n} \\
 P_{f_1f_1} \\
 P_{f_1f_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{f_1f_n} \\
 P_{f_1Q_1} \\
 P_{f_1Q_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{f_1Q_n} \\
 P_{f_21} \\
 P_{f_22} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{f_2n} \\
 P_{f_2e_1} \\
 P_{f_2e_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{f_2e_n} \\
 P_{f_2f_1} \\
 P_{f_2f_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{f_2f_n} \\
 P_{f_2Q_1} \\
 P_{f_2Q_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{f_2Q_n} \\
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 \vdots \\
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 P_{f_nf_1} \\
 P_{f_nf_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{f_nf_n} \\
 P_{f_nQ_1} \\
 P_{f_nQ_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{f_nQ_n} \\
 P_{Q_11} \\
 P_{Q_12} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{Q_1n} \\
 P_{Q_1e_1} \\
 P_{Q_1e_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{Q_1e_n} \\
 P_{Q_1f_1} \\
 P_{Q_1f_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{Q_1f_n} \\
 P_{Q_1Q_1} \\
 P_{Q_1Q_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{Q_1Q_n} \\
 P_{Q_21} \\
 P_{Q_22} \\
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 P_{Q_2e_n} \\
 P_{Q_2f_1} \\
 P_{Q_2f_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{Q_2f_n} \\
 P_{Q_2Q_1} \\
 P_{Q_2Q_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{Q_2Q_n} \\
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 \ddots \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{Q_ne_1} \\
 P_{Q_ne_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{Q_ne_n} \\
 P_{Q_nf_1} \\
 P_{Q_nf_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{Q_nf_n} \\
 P_{Q_nQ_1} \\
 P_{Q_nQ_2} \\
 \vdots \\
 P_{Q_nQ_n}
 \end{bmatrix}
 \begin{bmatrix}
 V_1 \\
 V_2 \\
 \vdots \\
 V_n \\
 e_1 \\
 e_2 \\
 \vdots \\
 e_n \\
 f_1 \\
 f_2 \\
 \vdots \\
 f_n \\
 Q_1 \\
 Q_2 \\
 \vdots \\
 Q_n
 \end{bmatrix}
 \quad (16)$$

The updated values are therefore calculated using equations (9) and (10) after getting the unknown vectors from equation (16). These are then used to find the updated value of the amount of reactive power needed to maintain the required voltage if the voltage limits are violated is given by

$$Q_{sh} = -V_i^2 \square b_{sh} + V_i \square V_{st} (b_{sh} \square \cos(\square_i - \square_{st}) - g_{sh} \square \sin(\square_i - \square_{st})) \tag{17}$$

where

$V_i = V_i \square \square_i$ = voltage at bus i

$V_{st} = V_{st} \square \square_{st}$ = voltage at the STATCOM bus

b_{sh} = STATCOM line susceptance g_{sh} = STATCOM line conductance

The Sample Network

Table 1: Bus data

Bus	Type	Vsp	Degree	QG	PG	QL	PL	Qmin	Qmax
30	3	1.0	0	0	0	1.9	10.6	0	0;
29	3	1.0	0	0	0	0.9	2.4	0	0;
28	3	1.0	0	0	0	0.0	0.0	0	0;
27	3	1.0	0	0	0	0.0	0.0	0	0;
26	3	1.0	0	0	0	2.3	3.5	0	0;
25	3	1.0	0	0	0	0.0	0.0	0	0;
24	3	1.0	0	0	0	6.7	8.7	0	0;
23	3	1.0	0	0	0	1.6	3.2	0	0;
22	3	1.0	0	0	0	0.0	0.0	0	0;
21	3	1.0	0	0	0	11.2	17.5	0	0;
20	3	1.0	0	0	0	0.7	2.2	0	0;
19	3	1.0	0	0	0	3.4	9.5	0	0;
18	3	1.0	0	0	0	0.9	3.2	0	0;
17	3	1.0	0	0	0	5.8	9.0	0	0;
16	3	1.0	0	0	0	1.8	3.5	0	0;
15	3	1.0	0	0	0	2.5	8.2	0	0;
14	3	1.0	0	0	0	1.6	6.2	0	0;
13	2	1.071	0	10.6	0	0.0	0.0	-6	24;
12	3	1.0	0	0	0	7.5	11.2	0	0;
11	2	1.082	0	16.2	0	0.0	0.0	-6	24;
10	3	1.0	0	0	0	2.0	5.8	0	0;
9	3	1.0	0	0	0	0.0	0.0	0	0;
8	2	1.01	0	37.3	0	30.0	30.0	-10	40;
7	3	1.0	0	0	0	10.9	22.8	0	0;
6	3	1.0	0	0	0	0.0	0.0	0	0;
5	2	1.01	0	37.0	0	19.0	94.2	-40	40;
4	3	1.0	0	0	0	1.6	7.6	0	0;
3	3	1.0	0	0	0	1.2	2.4	0	0;

2	2	1.043	0	50.0	40	12.7	21.7	-40	50;
1	1	1.06	0	0	0	0	0	0	0;

Table 2: Line Data

From Bus	To Bus	R (pu)	X (pu)	B/2 (pu)	Xmer (a)	TAP
4	12	0.0	0.2560	0.0	0.932	
9	10	0.0	0.1100	0.0	1	
9	11	0.0	0.2080	0.0	1	
From Bus	To Bus	R (pu)	X (pu)	B/2 (pu)	Xmer (a)	TAP
6	10	0.0	0.5560	0.0	0.969	
6	9	0.0	0.2080	0.0	0.978	
6	8	0.0120	0.0420	0.0045	1	
6	7	0.0267	0.0820	0.0085	1	
5	7	0.0460	0.1160	0.0102	1	
4	6	0.0119	0.0414	0.0045	1	
2	6	0.0581	0.1763	0.0187	1	
2	5	0.0472	0.1983	0.0209	1	
3	4	0.0132	0.0379	0.0042	1	
2	4	0.0570	0.1737	0.0184	1	
1	3	0.0452	0.1652	0.0204	1	
1	2	0.0192	0.0575	0.0264	1	
12	13	0.0	0.1400	0.0	1	
12	14	0.1231	0.2559	0.0	1	
12	15	0.0662	0.1304	0.0	1	
12	16	0.0945	0.1987	0.0	1	
14	15	0.2210	0.1997	0.0	1	
16	17	0.0824	0.1923	0.0	1	
15	18	0.1073	0.2185	0.0	1	
18	19	0.0639	0.1292	0.0	1	
19	20	0.0340	0.0680	0.0	1	
10	20	0.0936	0.2090	0.0	1	
10	17	0.0324	0.0845	0.0	1	

10	21	0.0348	0.0749	0.0	1
10	22	0.0727	0.1499	0.0	1
21	23	0.0116	0.0236	0.0	1
15	23	0.1000	0.2020	0.0	1
22	24	0.1150	0.1790	0.0	1
23	24	0.1320	0.2700	0.0	1
24	25	0.1885	0.3292	0.0	1
25	26	0.2544	0.3800	0.0	1
25	27	0.1093	0.2087	0.0	1
28	27	0.0000	0.3960	0.0	0.968
27	29	0.2198	0.4153	0.0	1
27	30	0.3202	0.6027	0.0	1
29	30	0.2399	0.4533	0.0	1
8	28	0.0636	0.2000	0.0214	1
6	28	0.0169	0.0599	0.065	1

Table 3: Statcom Data

Bus	V	Theta	Qsmx	Qsmn
14	1	0	0.5	-0.5;
24	1	0	0.5	-0.5;

Results and Discussion

The convergence was obtained after five iterations, and the results are shown in Tables 4 and 5, with corresponding maximum power-mismatch values of $3.317e-005$ and $3.926e-0.05$, respectively, for the same tolerance value of $1.000e-4$.

Tables 1, 2 and 3 show the input data for this analysis. Table 4 shows the outputs by running the developed MATLAB program using the standard IEEE 30-bus system.

Table 4: Power Flow Results

Voltage Profile without STATCOM using NewtonRaphson Method			Voltage Profile with STATCOM using Newton-Raphson Method	
Bus No	V (p.u)	Angle (Degree)	V (p.u)	Angle (Degree)
1	1.0600	0.000	1.0600	0.0000
2	1.0530	2.0372	1.0430	2.1494
3	1.0723	3.5500	1.0494	3.8586
4	1.0751	4.3369	1.0471	4.7577
5	1.0300	4.2917	1.0200	4.3943
6	1.0771	4.7942	1.0497	5.2163

7	1.0643	4.5513	1.0442	4.8159
8	1.0700	4.9910	1.0500	5.2974
9	1.1219	7.6193	1.0650	8.1938
10	1.1443	9.0568	1.0528	9.7986
11	1.1020	7.6193	1.0820	8.1938
12	1.1472	8.5527	1.0579	9.2626
13	1.1310	8.5527	1.0710	9.2626
14	1.1576	9.2305	1.0000	12.4162
15	1.1586	9.2981	1.0476	10.5160
16	1.1524	9.0043	1.0627	9.7711
17	1.1515	9.2148	1.0610	9.9958
18	1.1641	9.7697	1.0609	10.9266
19	1.1647	9.8966	1.0658	10.9840
20	1.1602	9.7388	1.0632	10.7454
21	1.1592	9.4650	1.0538	10.6666
22	1.1523	9.2559	1.0280	10.8180
23	1.1600	9.4674	1.0499	10.7966
24	1.1631	9.4441	1.0000	12.3938
25	1.1530	9.1011	1.0362	10.6079
26	1.1681	9.4180	1.0530	10.9990
27	1.1395	8.6637	1.0519	9.3501
28	1.0842	5.1813	1.0518	5.6808
29	1.1558	9.6235	1.0694	10.4741
30	1.1653	10.2770	1.0796	11.2366

Table 5: Buses Where STATCOMs are Applied

STATCOM Bus No	V_{SH} (p.u)	Angle (Degree)	Q_{SH} (p.u)
24	0.9437	12.7162	0.5628
14	0.9524	12.6889	0.4760

As can be seen in Table 4, without STATCOM, buses 9–30 exhibit overvoltage, as these values exceed the prescribed limits for this work, which are $\pm 5\%$ of the voltage base value. Based on these results, it is necessary to take control actions to prevent voltage collapse. Table 4, with and without STATCOM, shows the voltage profile before and after the bus voltages are corrected. Table 5 shows the values of buses 14 and 24 where STATCOMs are applied to correct the voltage magnitudes. The reactive power compensation applied by the STATCOM is done by the injection of reactive power of 0.4760 P.u and 0.5628 P.u at buses 14 and 24

respectively. Figure 3 and Figure 4 show the swing curves when faults are applied to buses 14 and 24 respectively. The behaviour of the system during a fault at buses 14 and 24 was investigated under the same clearing time of 0.1sec and simulation time of 2.0 secs by removing line 14-15 (Figure 3) and line 23-24 Figure 4.

Figure 3: fault at bus 14 and removal of line 14-15 with clearing time of 0.1sec and simulation time of 2.0secs

Figure 4: fault at bus 24 and removal of line 23-24 with clearing time of 0.1sec and simulation time of 2.0secs

Conclusions

This paper presents a methodology that aims to facilitate understanding of concepts related to transient stability with STATCOM. Load-flow analysis using the Newton-Raphson model. The behaviour of the system during faults at buses 14 and 24, respectively, was investigated under the same clearing time of 0.1sec and simulation time of 2.0 sec by removing line 14-15 (Figure 3) and line 23-24 (Figure 4). The Statcom model for the voltage stability analysis was proposed using the Newton-Raphson iterative method. The study is accomplished by considering a 30-bus system obtained from the standard IEEE. The behaviour of the system was investigated by introducing a fault at some buses of the standard 30-bus IEEE network under study, with constant clearing and simulation times, by removing the line on which the fault had occurred. The steady-state busvoltage values were determined from the load flow. The proposed STATCOM model was used to calculate the bus voltages in the standard IEEE 30-bus network. The values obtained from the two methods are compared, showing an improvement in the system bus voltages.

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